

Emerging adults were identified on the basis of wing markings.

Two species were found: *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and *Marasmia patnalis*. *C. medinalis* accounted for 53% and *M. patnalis* for 47% of the population (see table). *M. patnalis* predominated in Walajah, Thiruvannamalai, and Arakonam divisions; *C. medinalis* in the other divisions. □

Persistence of quinalphos in rice

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We studied the persistence of quinalphos in rice variety Lalat following foliar spraying during 1984-85 kharif and rabi. Quinalphos was sprayed at 0.5 kg ai/ha and 1.0 kg ai/ha, with 3 replications. Plant samples were extracted by chloroform, cleaned by celite:MgO:charcoal column, and

Table 1. Quinalphos residue in rice, 1984-85 dry season (rabi), Bhubaneswar, India.

Days after treatment	Quinalphos residue ^a (ppm)	
	0.5 kg ai/ha	1.0 kg ai/ha
0	5.3	9.5
5	2.5	3.1
10	0.5	1.0
15	n.d.	0.25
20	n.d.	n.d.
50% residue level (d)	3	3

^a n.d. = not detectable.

Table 2. Quinalphos residue in rice, 1985 wet season (kharif), Bhubaneswar, India.

Days after treatment	Quinalphos residue (ppm)	
	0.5 kg ai/ha	1.0 kg ai/ha
0	4.23	6.53
5	1.74	2.71
10	0.27	0.69
15	n.d.	0.34
20	n.d.	n.d.
50% residue level (d)	2.5	3.0

estimated by spectrophotometric method. Recoveries from fortified samples were 80-85%

Initial deposits of quinalphos in rice plant samples were reduced to

nondetectable levels within 15-20 d after treatment during the dry season (Table 1) and within 15-20 d after treatment during the wet season (Table 2). □

Insecticides to control rice hispa

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We evaluated eight insecticides against rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) in a duplicated farmer's field trial during kharif 1986. Plot size was 100 m².

Live grub population from 10 hills/plot was recorded before insecticide application and 1 wk after. Adult beetle population and percent leaf damage on all leaves in 10 hills/plot were assessed 2 wk after insecticide application.

Monocrotophos at 0.06% was most effective against hispa grubs, closely followed by quinalphos at 0.07%. Adult beetle population also was checked by monocrotophos followed by quinalphos (see table). □

Chemical control of rice hispa in Warangal district, Andhra Pradesh, India.^a

Treatment	Grubs/hill		% reduction of grubs	Adults/hill at 14 d after application	% leaf damage
	Before application	7 d after application			
Carbofuran 3G @ 25 kg/ha	12	1 a	87 a	0.4 ab	0.1 ab
Phorate 10G @ 10 kg/ha	9	3 a	60 ab	1.2 b	0.9 ab
Monocrotophos 40EC @ 0.06%	11	1 a	94 a	0.2 a	0.3 ab
Chlorpyrifos 20EC @ 0.06%	7	2 a	69 ab	0.6 ab	0.0 a
Endosulfan 35EC @ 0.09%	12	6 b	42 b	6.8 d	8.0 c
Fenvalerate 20EC @ 0.01%	10	2 a	83 ab	2.5 c	1.8 b
Phosalone 35EC @ 0.09%	10	1 a	89 a	0.8 ab	0.4 ab
Quinalphos 25EC @ 0.07%	10	1 a	92 a	0.3 ab	0.1 ab
Untreated control	10	11 c	-8 c	7.0 d	8.4 c
F test	ns	**	**	**	**
CD (0.05)	-	2	(26)	1.0	(5.70)

^a In a column, values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly. Figures in parentheses are transformed values.

Egg parasites of *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) in Sri Lanka

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We studied the yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) in Mar and Jul 1982 at the Dryzone Agricultural Research Station, Maha Illuppallama, Sri Lanka. After transplanting, experimental plots were covered with mesh cages. Two weeks after transplanting, plots were exposed

for YSB oviposition. The experiment was repeated four times in two seasons.

Hatched egg masses were collected on day four, remaining egg masses were collected on day eight and held in glass vials in the laboratory. Number of parasites emerging from each egg mass was recorded. Then, egg masses were soaked in 5% HCl and separated into individual eggs and number of hatched eggs, unenclosed dead larvae, and unemerged parasites recorded. Parasites were sent to the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology for identification.

Telenomus sp. and *Tetrastichus*

schoenobii Ferriere were the only egg parasites obtained from 193 egg masses (1,070 eggs) of *S. incertulas* (see table). Although *Telenomus* sp. caused a higher percentage of parasitization than *T. schoenobii* in all four generations (*S. incertulas* completes two generations each cropping season in Sri Lanka), the difference was not significant. □

Parasitization of *S. incertulas* eggs by *Telenomus* sp. and *T. schoenobii*. Maha Illuppallama, Sri Lanka, May and Jul, 1982.

Generation	Eggs (no.)	Parasitization (%)		
		<i>Telenomus</i> sp.	<i>T. schoenobii</i>	Total
1st	208	27.0	17.3	44.3
2d	195	27.4	16.0	43.4
3d	345	36.3	24.5	60.8
4th	322	35.3	23.3	58.6

Diluted quinalphos and fenthion and control of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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Two experiments with two insecticides (quinalphos and fenthion) were conducted to evaluate diluted insecticides in controlling WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* at Bhupindra Rice Research Substation, Rauni, 1985 wet season.

Recommended rate (0.5 kg ai/ha) of quinalphos and fenthion was diluted with water to apply 250, 375, and 500 liters/ha. A randomized block design with four replications for quinalphos and three for fenthion was used. Plot size was 300 m².

WBPH counts at 2 and 8 d after application for quinalphos and 2 d after application for fenthion showed no significant differences among treatments (see table). □

Effect of diluted insecticides on WBPH incidence. Punjab, India, 1985.

Treatment	WBPH ^a (adults + nymphs)/10 hills		
	Pre-treatment ^b	2 d after application	8 d after application
Quinalphos 25 EC			
250	174 a	11 a	80 a
375	171 a	9 a	84 a
500	174 a	4 a	101 a
Control	184 a	200 b	273 b
Fenthion 1000 EC			
250	211 a	11 a	—
375	189 a	9 a	—
500	175 a	10 a	—
Control	182 a	294 b	—

^aFor each group of insecticide treatments, means in a column followed by a common letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b30 Aug for quinalphos and 5 Sep for fenthion.

***Nisaga simplex* caterpillar on rice in western Orissa**

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Hairy caterpillar *Nisaga simplex* Wlk. (Eupterotidae: Lepidoptera) regularly damages upland and medium ricefields in various locations of Kalahandi and Koraput districts in the wet season Jun-Dec. Moths emerged in Jun with the onset of the monsoon and oviposit on weedy growth of scrubby jungles and on adjoining ricefields. Incubation lasted 7-9 d. In the laboratory, 8 larval instars were completed in 68-76 d. Pupation took place in soil. Caterpillars fed

voraciously on the leaf lamina, leaving only the midrib.

In its natural habitat, the pest pupated in loose lateritic soil, often as deep as 30 cm, in Oct and overwintered to the following Jun. The caterpillars shunned water and did not migrate to lowland fields. The moths are poor fliers.

Weedy fields attracted higher populations than weeded fields. The caterpillars also attacked maize, sorghum, finger millet, sugarcane, and these weed species: *Brachiaria mutica*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *Digitaria ciliaris*, *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *E. glabrescens*, *Eleusine indica*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Panicum repens*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, *P. clisticum*, and *P. scrobiculatum*. □

Rice leaffolder (LF) infestations in West Bengal

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Rice LF generally appears as a minor pest of rice in West Bengal. However, it

infested over 67,000 ha in 11 districts in 1986, causing appreciable damage to standing wet season rice. All the districts experiencing massive infestation were located on the south and southwest sides of the river Ganges.

Cnaphalocrocis medinalis (Guenée) was the most dominant LF species;

Leaves damaged by LF, maximum and minimum temperatures, and rainfall in different months.^a West Bengal, India.

Month	Damaged leaves (%)	Mean monthly temperature (°C)		Rainfall (mm)
		Maximum	Minimum	
May	3.6	34.5 (-1.9)	22.3 (-2.7)	178.8 (+63.4)
Jun	5.5	34.3 (+0.4)	26.6 (+1.1)	278.6 (+30.0)
Jul	12.6	31.5 (-0.2)	25.9 (+0.2)	249.5 (-40.2)
Aug	31.3	32.7 (+1.4)	26.3 (+0.6)	98.2 (-404.4)
Sep	73.6	31.4 (-0.1)	25.1 (-0.4)	750.0 (+513.5)
Oct	31.9	30.6 (-0.4)	22.1 (-0.8)	104.3 (-8.0)

^aMean of 20 samples. Figures in the parentheses indicate deviations from normal.